

MODERNIZATION PROCESSES IN LEGAL AND NORMATIVE BASIS OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN.

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Annotation. Since the first years of independence, the development of the education system in our country has been elevated to the level of state policy, and great efforts have been made to ensure that our children acquire modern knowledge and professions in conditions that meet world standards, grow up as physically and spiritually mature people, realize their abilities, talents, and intellectual potential, and cultivate feelings of loyalty and selflessness to the motherland in the hearts of our youth.

Keywords: education, upbringing, value, "Law on Education", continuing education, individual, state, society.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated April 20, 2017 - On measures for the further development of the higher education system is significant in that it is both a logical continuation of the work being carried out to reform the education system in our country and is aimed at raising it to a new level. One of the most important aspects of the Resolution is that it pays special attention to compliance with international standards in the training of highly qualified specialists, creating conditions at its level, and training personnel with modern knowledge and skills in accordance with the spirit and requirements.

Therefore, pedagogical personnel working in educational institutions should be well-versed in the optimal organization of teaching forms, enriching the theory of the formation of a well-rounded personality with various new ideas. The implementation of the ideas of the "National Program for Personnel Training" into practice, the success of the reforms being carried out in the education system of our country, largely depend on the spiritual image and professional skills of teachers working in the education system.

In the social policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the realization of national identity, the creation of harmony between the individual and society through the assimilation of national and universal values, the satisfaction of the transition of needs from individual to general require the study and development of the abilities, talents, internal capabilities, and specific individual-psychological characteristics of young people

reaching adulthood in all respects. It is impossible to increase the effectiveness of the process of secondary specialized and higher education and upbringing without determining the formation, mental development, and level of upbringing of the younger generation as a person and subject.

The establishment of democratic principles in the infrastructure of society, in group interpersonal relations, the beginning of the criteria of equality, subjectivity, cooperation, empathy among citizens to become a way of life is a vivid expression of the global socio-historical victory of the human world.

In the present era, the end of the robotization of the individual, the establishment of a material and spiritual foundation for his manifestation as an independent person (subject), the acquisition of a personal worldview (both scientific and religious), stable beliefs, a strong position, a firm will, a sharp and unbending idea have created an opportunity. Such a social reality, phenomenon, social imagination and need of universal significance, the recognition of the individual as a central figure in our country and the assessment of him as a driving force of development, mean that pedagogical knowledge has become a necessity.

In the field of humanities, since it requires interaction in the form of man-society, society-man, it is permissible to establish both direct and inverse relationships between the first and the second. As Abdulla Avloni predicted in his time: "If pedagogy wants to educate a person in all respects, then it is necessary to study a person in all respects." Therefore, in the process of education, it is necessary to form a well-rounded person, through its result, product, it is permissible to develop an independent thinker, creative seeker, strong-willed, hardworking, ideologically convinced, highly spiritual, and conscientious person.

Because without practically resolving the "subject-subject" relationship, we will not be able to determine the level of education. In this regard, pedagogy is of great importance, and this is the condition for it to correspond to the goal of society to cultivate a well-rounded person.

The statement of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov: "Only if we can educate intelligent, highly spiritual people can we achieve the goals we have set for ourselves, and prosperity and development will prevail in our country," shows that improving education and enlightenment, raising a new generation that will realize the national ideal, is one of the most important tasks of our state.

To implement these ambitious tasks, the IX session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic on August 29, 1997 adopted the Law "On Education", which served as a legal basis, and the "National Program for Personnel Training".

The adoption of the "Law on Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan was due to a number of factors: firstly, the social system in our environment has changed, secondly, the attitude towards social production and property has changed, thirdly, old ideological views have ceased to meet new conditions, and fourthly, the activities carried out in educational institutions have required organization in accordance with world standards, instilling in students a sense of national and universal values, and preparing them as comprehensively well-rounded, deeply knowledgeable specialists. As is known, the Law "On Education" consists of 5 sections and 34 articles. The main principles of state policy in the field of education are: education is declared a priority in the field of social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, therefore, educational work is one of the main principles of state policy.

The main principles of state policy in the field of education are:

- the humane democratic nature of education and upbringing;
- the continuity and consistency of education;
- the compulsory nature of general secondary, as well as secondary specialized, vocational education;
- the voluntary nature of choosing the direction of secondary specialized, vocational education;
- the secular nature of the education system;
- the openness of education to everyone within the framework of state educational standards;
- a unified and differentiated approach to the choice of educational programs;
- the promotion of literacy and talent;
- the harmonization of state and public administration in the education system.

The goal of the reforms being implemented in the field of education is to raise a well-rounded generation.

"First of all, we need to fundamentally change our attitude towards the education system. Education reform must be an internal force that boldly leads us along the path of democratic changes and building a new society, moving us all. Let each of us know as clearly as five fingers, as the old saying goes, nine coins, that without changing the education system, it is impossible to change the minds of people, and therefore their lifestyle."

Our Head of State has touched upon the necessity and importance of education reform in a number of his speeches.

In his speech at the IX session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 29, 1997, our Head of State stated that the measures implemented so far do not

meet the requirements, that we have not been able to completely get rid of the ideological views and stereotypes inherent in the education system left over from the old Soviet era, secondly, the changes are superficial and do not solve the problems of linking the structure and stages of education and training processes with each other, that is, organizing a continuous education system, thirdly, our current education system cannot meet the requirements of today's modern, developed democratic countries... etc. also showed the need for this reform. In this regard, our Head of State, in his speech on the topic "A well-developed generation is the foundation of Uzbekistan's development", justified the need and factors for reforming the education system.

The purpose of the Law on Education is to establish the legal basis for education, upbringing, vocational training of citizens, and to ensure the constitutional right of everyone to receive knowledge.

Section 1 of the Law is called "General Provisions". It reflects the basic principles of state policy in the field of education, the rights to receive knowledge, engage in pedagogical activities, the legal status of an educational institution, DTS, and the language of instruction.

Section 2 of the Law "On Education" covers the essence of the education system and its types.

The education system in our republic includes: state and non-state educational institutions implementing educational programs in accordance with state educational standards; scientific and pedagogical institutions carrying out research work necessary to ensure the development of the education system; state management bodies in the field of education, as well as enterprises, institutions and organizations affiliated with them.

Article 10 of this law states that education shall be implemented in the following types. Section 2, Articles 11-17 of the law briefly outline the essence of each educational stage. As it is noted, preschool education aims to form a healthy and mature personality of the child, prepared for school. Preschool education is implemented in state and non-state preschool institutions and families until the child reaches the age of six or seven. General secondary education is compulsory and is implemented at the following stages: primary education (grades I-IV); general secondary education (grades I-IX). General secondary education forms the systematic knowledge of students in the basics of subjects, the need for knowledge acquisition, basic academic, scientific and general cultural knowledge, spiritual and moral qualities based on national and universal values, labor skills, creative thinking and a conscious attitude to the environment, and the choice of profession. "Upon completion of general secondary education, a

certificate of a state-approved sample is issued indicating the subjects studied and the grades received in them."

The law states that everyone has the right to voluntarily choose the direction of study at an academic lyceum or vocational college on the basis of general secondary education for the purpose of obtaining secondary specialized, vocational education. "Academic lyceums and vocational colleges provide secondary specialized, vocational education, which gives the right to work in the acquired profession and serves as the basis for continuing such work or education at the next stage." In academic lyceums, students have the opportunity to improve their knowledge in the chosen field of education and develop special professional skills aimed at in-depth study of the subject. They can continue their studies at certain higher educational institutions or implement these skills in their work. Vocational colleges provide secondary specialized, vocational education within the framework of relevant state educational standards; they allow students to develop their professional inclinations, knowledge and skills, and acquire one or more specialties in the chosen profession.

Higher education trains highly qualified specialists, is carried out at two levels: bachelor's and master's degrees.

The third section of the law is devoted to the social protection of participants in the educational process, in which the issues of social protection of students and employees of educational institutions, education of orphans and children with disabilities in physical and mental development are legally reflected.

The fourth section indicates the powers of the Cabinet of Ministers, state bodies authorized to manage education and local government bodies in managing the education system, and the fifth section contains the final provisions.

The national model of personnel training and its essence On August 29, 1997, at the IX session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On Education" and the "National Program for Personnel Training" were adopted. They provided the main guidelines for reforming the education and upbringing and personnel training system.

As is known, the "National Program for Personnel Training" consists of five sections, which define the factors of reforming the personnel training system, the purpose of the program, "tasks and stages of its implementation, the main directions of development of the personnel training system, and measures for the implementation of the program. Section 3 of the program highlights the essence of the national model of personnel training. The main components of the national model of personnel training are as follows.

"Person" - the main subject and object of the personnel training system, the consumer of services in the field of education and their implementer". State policy in the field of personnel training envisages the formation of a comprehensively developed individual-citizen through a system of continuous education, which is inextricably linked with the intellectual and spiritual and moral upbringing of a person. In this way, one of the most basic constitutional rights of a citizen is realized - the right to obtain knowledge, demonstrate creative abilities, develop intellectually, and work in his profession.

As a consumer of educational services, a person is guaranteed education and vocational training by the state. In the educational process, a person must fulfill the requirements set forth in state educational standards. As a provider of educational services, a person, having received an appropriate level of qualification, is engaged in teaching knowledge and experience to the younger generation in the educational process, in the fields of material production, science, culture and household services.

Each person is formed as a person only through the system of education, social upbringing and spiritual development, and vocational training.

As a result, a person achieves social maturity - his performance of useful functions for society, a thorough and creative understanding of his tasks and duties, and the entry into equal, independent relations with others.

The place and role of a person, rights and obligations in the personnel training system are constitutionally strengthened, legally protected and systematically spelled out in relevant documents.

"State and Society" is the guarantor of personnel training and admission, which regulates and controls the activities of the education and personnel training system, and coordinates the activities of educational institutions in the training of highly qualified competitive specialists."

The state and society guarantee the following, such as:

- the right of citizens to receive education, their opportunities for choosing a profession and improving their qualifications;

compulsory general secondary and secondary specialized, vocational education, which gives the right to choose a direction of study in academic lyceums or vocational colleges;

- the right to receive higher and higher education on the basis of state grants or on a fee-based basis;

financial support for state educational institutions;

- development of public administration to address issues of ensuring the conditions for studying, living and relaxing for students;

social support for participants in the educational process;

- the active implementation of regulatory legal acts on increasing the responsibility of pedagogical staff of educational institutions and parents for the upbringing and protection of children's lives. Thus, high-quality professional training, social incentives and protection for an individual, and assistance in emergencies are guaranteed by the state.

“Continuous education” is the basis for the training of qualified competitive personnel and includes all types of education: preschool education, general secondary education, secondary specialized, vocational education, higher education, post-university education, advanced training and retraining of personnel, out-of-school education, DTS, the structure of the personnel training system and its operating environment.

The continuous education system should meet the various educational needs of a person and society, create broad opportunities for raising the value and status of knowledge, and also provide fundamental knowledge and social protection of the individual by training specialists on a general educational, general cultural, professional and scientific basis in the conditions of changing needs of the economy.

The directions of reforming continuing education were identified as a radical improvement of the human resources potential of the education system, the development of various types of state and non-state educational institutions, ensuring the transition from compulsory general secondary education to secondary specialized, vocational education, improving the education management system, creating a system for objective assessment of the quality of the educational process and personnel training, expanding cooperation with foreign and international organizations related to education and science.

Science is directly involved in radically updating the content of education, preparing educational standards, educational programs, textbooks and manuals, and implementing scientific and methodological support. In addition, science, as a customer in personnel training, achieves direct correlation of scientific research with the educational process.

"Production" is the main customer, which determines the need for personnel, as well as the requirements for the quality and level of their training, a participant in the process of providing the personnel training system in financial and material and technical terms. "Production, performing the functions of a customer and consumer in the personnel training system, actively participates in the process of training, retraining and advanced training of personnel at the required high levels and for relevant industries.

The needs of production form the social order for personnel training, determine the purpose, tasks and content of vocational training, put forward qualification requirements, determine the conditions for choosing new technologies and forms of training. Production ultimately assesses the quality and competitiveness of personnel. The state and society ensure that the system of continuing education and personnel training is open to all and adaptable to life changes. Taking into account advanced world experience in the field of personnel training affects all aspects of the system of continuing education and personnel training and is one of the factors of its development.

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